

Interview transcript STE *Norms and values*

Interview date: 15.05.2023, 24.05.2023

Participants: P10

I [00:00:02] Okay. So regarding time. So I planned for around one and a half hours. Maybe we a little bit faster because we are only two people, but in general it's about 15 minutes introduction, 60 minutes interview and 15 minutes again feedback and reflection. Um, so I will quickly introduce myself. So my name is I [interviewer]. I'm, I'm a student at the University of Osnabrück, and the program is called Environment Systems and Resource Management. And I'm currently writing my thesis in collaboration with the Potsdam Institute of Climate Impact Research, and that's how I got in contact with Decade of Action. and so you in the end and the topic of my thesis is social tipping for regenerative agriculture. And I am personally, I was always interested in like the social and environmental processes at the same time. So I kind of ended up in the agricultural research field and I have the feeling that, yeah, regenerative agriculture that can have a big impact regarding biodiversity, climate change and so on. So yeah, I would like to ask you to introduce yourself quickly with your professional background and also your professional or personal relation to regenerative agriculture.

P10 [00:01:31] Yeah. My name is P10 I am more on. Less. On this thing. Long term landscape of restoration, including promotion of regenerative agriculture as a contribution to that. My background is in cultural anthropology and development, so looking into the the protocol of international cooperation. And then I also, like you said, I was really interested in the social and natural processes interacting. So how do we organise ourselves as human beings in such a way? (incomprehensible). So good examples, bad examples. I looked into land rights, fishing rights, community land rights, but also wildlife. Of small scale agriculture versus (incomprehensible). I worked for 4 to 5 years on international advocacy around the promotion of sustainable agriculture and mostly small scale farming. And then I switched to common land. More on the landscape scale. So that's where I'm at now. And I focus the (incomprehensible).

I [00:03:06] Thank you very much. So sometimes I can't understand you so well. And so in between, like, a super good. But then it's a bit a. It struggles a bit.

P10 [00:03:16] Ok..

I [00:03:18] But I don't know if I mean, it's okay. It just.

P10 [00:03:21] I can change. It's better?

I [00:03:27] Uh, yeah, I think so. Yeah. I have a feeling it's a little better. Let's try.

P10 [00:03:40] Again. Let's try.

I [00:03:42] Yes. Thank you very much for the introduction. I will quickly explain to you the objectives of the interview and also the methodology. And so regarding the objectives. In the workshops last year. Uh, you have conducted a lot of, uh, we looked at interventions in the tipping dynamics in different areas of land use system, so in education, finance, policy. And so this interview will focus on the norms and values system. Um, and for me, this STE includes processes that change, the current norms and values system from conventional to regenerative among farmers, but also within the whole society. So that's how I define it for myself a little bit. Um. And so the goal is really to find out how exactly the interventions that were collected last year in the workshops contribute to create conditions that are necessary to accelerate this transition to agriculture with a special focus on the norms and value system. And I know that there are a lot of different definitions of regenerative agriculture. So I just decided for one and I will post it in the chat and if you have huge objections, we can discuss it. But I would rather prefer to continue. And so I will quickly copy it.

P10 [00:05:13] And just I hope I have been with the norms and values, but I don't remember. (incomprehensive)

I [00:05:24] Yeah, but, I mean, it's not. I mean, if you're interested in norms and value, it's okay. I mean, it's no problem. Yeah. Okay, So that's the definition I decided for for now.

P10 [00:05:42] Yeah.

I [00:05:53] Is it? Okay?

P10 [00:05:55] Okay.

I [00:05:55] Perfect. And so the output of this interview will also be like something like mind maps or diagrams, similar to the workshops last year. And I will use these diagrams to analyse the effects of different interventions. And also my goal is to combine different diagrams. So I want to have diagram from norms and values system now and then from education, for example, and I try to find a connection there. So I start with individual STEs and then I try to combine them. And so for the methodology, I will share my screen. It might be a little bit small, but you can put it on full screen and just leave your microphone on so you don't have to switch and you should be able to read it. Yeah. Yeah. And always let me know if you can read anything. It's sometimes a little bit difficult. Um, so I

organised the elements in three categories. Um, so first there are the. So first there are the interventions. So this is a collection of elements that were named during the workshop last year in the context of norms and values system. And then we have conditions. And conditions are also elements that I extracted from the workshop results, but also from literature. And these are elements that are considered to help social tipping to happen. So to enable the transition to regenerative agriculture and to make maybe the difference between interventions, conditions a bit more explicit and so conditions are elements that need to be fulfilled so that the transition process can happen, for example, that more people recognise values, for nature, agriculture, food, agriculture and food and interventions are really concrete measures, how these conditions can be fulfilled. So for example, influencers. Is it more or less clear this differentiation between these two?

P10 [00:08:16] Yeah. Yeah.

I [00:08:18] Okay. And I will give you a little bit time later to read through the post-its so that you can get familiar with them. And so consequences is a kind of a free space of positive elements that result from the condition. So what happens when more people recognise values, for example. And for the interview, we will go through these categories step by step, but also look at the whole diagram together. And in the workshop last year, you've collected a lot of different elements. So the goal of this interview is really to focus on the interconnections between the different elements. So identify the links between interventions, conditions and consequences, but also identify links between the elements within these categories. So, for example, links between these interventions. And it's also possible to add new elements. So if you think there's something missing, you can just add an element. And sometimes also necessary to add elements to find these connections. Hmm. Yeah. And for the interconnections, I would like us to follow a certain guideline which is now down here. So an arrow always shows that one element influences another. And there are two kind of arrows or there are positive and negative arrows. And the positive arrow means that if an element A increases, B also increases. If an element A decreases, B also decreases. And if there's a negative sign, the two variables change in opposite directions. So if A increases, B decreases and A decreases, B increases. So if we look at an example um so if the public knowledge or awareness of regenerative agriculture increases, we could assume that more people recognise the value for nature, agriculture and food. So in most of the cases we deal with positive arrows because we want to find out the interventions. But sometimes we will see, we also need the negative arrows. Um, are there any questions regarding this?

P10 [00:10:49] (incomprehensive).

I [00:10:49] Sorry. Can you.

P10 [00:10:54] Can you give an example of a negative?

I [00:10:56] Mm hmm. For example, I have a green post-it here. It's the dominance of conventional agriculture, and I would assume if the dominance of conventional agriculture increase less farmers would recognise the value of regenerative agriculture. So then there's like an opposite direction. So it increases if like dominance increases value for regenerative agriculture decreases.

P10 [00:11:25] Yes. Okay. Yeah.

I [00:11:28] Okay. Perfect. So now I would give you few minutes to read through the positives that are in there. And if there are any terms that are clear, please let me know. And then let me also know when you're done.

P10 [00:11:47] Yeah. Um. Would you like me to. What would you like me to do, set them or.

I [00:12:45] Um, so the idea is that we go through these categories step by step. So we start with the conditions. Then we go to the interventions and then we talk about the consequences. So there will be time when we talk about the interventions to also reflect on the different interventions if that works for you.

P10 [00:13:05] To start with intervention.

I [00:13:07] You would like to start with intervention?

P10 [00:13:12] (incomprehensive).

I [00:13:14] And so for me, the conditions are kind of the main like we have to influence the conditions. That's why I always start with the conditions in the middle to see what what is really needed for the transitioning process to happen in terms of the norms and value system. And so what kind of things need to evolve. And then we look at interventions, okay, how can we reach these goals.

P10 [00:14:37] Okay, Let's start the conversation.

I [00:14:39] Okay. Perfect. So is it okay for you to start with the conditions?

P10 [00:14:46] Yeah.

I [00:14:47] Okay, so I think I repeat myself, but here we really want to focus on what is needed to accelerate the transition to regenerative agriculture with regard to the norms and values system, and I already highlighted two conditions because they kind of directly take norms and values system into account. So one is farmers recognising value in regenerative agriculture and the other one is the people of that whole population recognising values for nature, agriculture and food. And so my question is, if you think these conditions are important, if you would add some conditions or yeah, what are your thoughts regarding these four post-its.

P10 [00:15:40] I think they make sense. I mean. (incomprehensive) to become more open towards regenerative agriculture is a condition for the farmers to become more aware. Let's say you're (incomprehensive). So you are doing everything regenerative agriculture school taught you? So, how, what are the conditions for (incomprehensive) an alternative? Um, I think there's a need for a sense of inspiration and exposure to other alternatives and alternatives that are feasible, that they make some logical sense. But most importantly, they inspire me (incomprehensive). The inspiration might not be rational. I would just be inspired by an alternative that is feasible, viable, but also bring back (incomprehensive) and beautiful product products and a healthy soil (incomprehensive). That potential of an alternative future. That is for me, the number one condition. And for me to be inspired and I need to feel. I think a sense of connection to other farmers, of course, you can watch a YouTube video of regenerative agriculture and then say, Oh that's cool and I like. But for me (incomprehensive) right (incomprehensive) alternatives. And that can be in a conversation with your former neighbour. But it could also be (incomprehensive). It could be by interacting with another organisation, an NGO that shows you the alternative (incomprehensive) future. That's (incomprehensive). Next ist (incomprehensive) or getting more knowledge. So it's inspiration and getting knowledge, starting to come out and starting to see the changes over time. And so there's is a bit of a loop you take action or you you join a learning network and then because you've taken that action you are really inspired. So it's like this positive cycle that you get into. And I think that's (incomprehensive) if I'm a farmer and I believe, like what I'm doing (incomprehensive). Of course I'm going to be (incomprehensive) a new idea? When I'm struggling, if I see that I'm suffering and I need to perform with fertilizer and pesticides, and if I have more input on my farm than I had ten years ago, then I also start to wonder, does this business model make sense? So there's needs to be a sense of (incomprehensive) that the current path can't continue forever. So there needs to be this latent owners that (incomprehensive).

I [00:19:59] Mm hmm. Sorry. I think I could maybe try to reconnect to the to the meeting room, because sometimes I really it's really, really hard to understand you. And I think you're saying really interesting things. And I'm like, I can't.

P10 [00:20:20] Yeah. I try to reconnect.

I [00:20:20] Yeah. Perfect. Thank you very much.

P10 [00:20:51] Now?

I [00:20:53] Yeah, Sometimes it's really good. I mean, sometimes I just, like, it's super interrupted, so I'm.

P10 [00:21:02] Is it better a little bit?

I [00:21:02] Oh, yeah. I have the feeling. Yes. Okay. Okay. Let's try.

P10 [00:21:08] Let's try it again.

I [00:21:10] Yeah, it's better. It seems much better. Nice. And I tried to write down what you said a little bit on post-its, but I think I missed the last part. So I think you said something about the future like that. The future conditions are relevant. So that the farmer sees.

P10 [00:21:31] Yeah.

I [00:21:32] Could you maybe repeat?

P10 [00:21:33] I think if you asked if I would summarise it, it's almost with so few moments in your life, are you? Transformational change. You either change jobs or you break up with someone or you decide to go on a world travel trip. And so that's this moment in your life where you have to have a certain path which brought you to this moment. Um. And you need to be. Let's say if I'm open. You need to be open for change. Mm hmm. And when is someone looking for change? You can't really plan for that. But you can create conditions to become open. (incomprehensible) this is for me. (incomprehensible) and I've been talking about a farmer. So because (incomprehensible) if I could connect with fellow actors in an open way. And we talk about climate change and butterflies. (incomprehensible) I can do whatever I want. And then screw you. And I'm going to do what I want. So the farmers, I think it's the same it needs to be created this sort of open space. And it can be through a facilitation of group processes. It can be through farming (incomprehensible). And then you become more open as a person instead of very sick (incomprehensible) a different mindset to be open to alternatives. And once you. People seem to question what they're doing.

I [00:23:41] Mm hmm.

P10 [00:23:45] Be. Yeah. More open to alternatives and likely take them up. Mm hmm. And if you do that, you can also do that in society, you know, through a public space. I mean, you in in the newspapers, it's about having this open dialogue on what do we think the future of farming should be? What does the science say? What does the farmer say? What is the Ministry of Agriculture saying? Can we have a debate, like a societal debate, (incomprehensive) but also kitchen table conversation? And I think from the kitchen table, up until the national government and all those layers, it's almost like the (incomprehensive). If the societal debate moves in a certain direction. Um, slowly, slowly. norms and values start to change. You see it around gender rights, you see it around racism. I mean, it is no different from the way we look at something. So it's about having a (incomprehensive) the farmer and his or her daughter who wants to take over the farm. And of course, we're going to have forward momentum. And the backlash always there is always a response. Right. So that responses. Since (incomprehensive) there is such a heated debate around (incomprehensive). Protests, the sustainability debate. I'm just going to keep ploughing and doing intensive agriculture because I believe that's the way forward. And I think the sustainable model and they're never going to work. So we have negative feedback loops and the positive feedback loop. And once I think a critical mass of people have been, have opened themselves up for change and alternative futures and you have enough practical examples of people going on that road to regenerative agriculture and it starts to become like a critical mass. And for me, a good integration of regenerative agriculture in the Netherlands is when I watch the Daily News. And I see an item on regenerative agriculture. Now it's there. Yeah, it's not just an niche you account here in there. Or a really cool website or one or two initiatives. It's actually like, if it reaches the national television news, then you realise. Oh.

I [00:26:41] Can I maybe suggest, if we like call. Can I call you somehow because it's still sometimes I. It's really interrupted.

P10 [00:26:49] Sure. Could we use zoom?

I [00:26:51] Yea the problem is I'm not allowed to use zoom because of data protection reasons. Um, but I think it's I mean it's in Europe. So I think if I. Yeah. Perfect. So if you're just. Yeah. Let me know your number. I, I can, I can let your, my number and then you can call me.

P10 [00:27:12] Okay. I'll grab my air phone. Just one second.

I [00:27:51] So I think it would be good to just mute ourselves here and then we can work on the screen, but not talking. Thank you very much.

I [00:28:32] Hello?

P10 [00:28:34] Hey.

I [00:28:35] Yeah? Can you hear me good?

P10 [00:28:38] Yep.

I [00:28:38] Perfect.

P10 [00:28:40] Is this ok for the recording?

I [00:28:41] Yeah, I hope so. Yeah, I will make it. I increase your volume and I think then I hope my laptop will capture. Okay. I think it's much better. Thank you very much.

P10 [00:28:55] No problem. No problem. Should you turn your mice [micerophone] on to record.

I [00:29:02] So I have my my phone on speaker so it's loud and I hope that my because I record with my laptop so I hope that my laptop captures the speaker from my phone.

P10 [00:29:13] And so without turning on your mice?

I [00:29:16] Um, yeah, without turning on my mice.

P10 [00:29:20] Okay. All right.

I [00:29:21] Perfect. Thank you. So I would really like to try to capture what you said on this map. Um. Um, I try to follow what you said and try to put it down, but you also talked about loops, and I really would like to capture these loops. So if you could help me to maybe, um. Yeah. Map what you just said. So I understand, okay, inspiration is important. And also I added learning networks and connection between farmers. But I think I didn't capture where the loop occurs so maybe you could.

P10 [00:30:05] So I think where it all starts is this openness or readiness for change. Right?

I [00:30:14] Mm hmm.

P10 [00:30:15] So a society o a sector, like the farming sector needs to be ready for change. And that is a mix of urgency, timing, evolution of the sector. And I mean ten years ago, the timing was not right. Everybody was, like, (incomprehensive) believing that industrial farming is the future. But

now we see this readiness for change. So that's where it all starts, I feel. So that's kind of like, is the field that you are operating in, is there fertile soil for change? And that's a mix of a mix of things. But within that field of change, you want to create. Yeah. You also said here with the interventions kind of spaces for. Should something like spaces school.

I [00:31:15] Experimental outside spaces?

P10 [00:31:18] Right. Exactly. So at some point you need to have. And often you see this coming up bottom-up. There is a lot of like farmer networks emerging because they sense that change is coming and they don't want farmers to do it on their own. So they start these networks where there's such a collaboration looking at alternatives, where farmers are already doing it differently, where you can learn from that. So, you see this interaction between this field that is ready for change and the people interacting with in that field are starting to connect to each other. And then you get this point where you're going to have more and more farmers that are feel the sense of that something needs to be done, but they don't know how yet and they don't know what needs to change. But then it's providing these opportunities for inspiration, and that can either be through, yeah, something you see on the news, another farmer you visit and a NGO you get in touch with a movie that you'll watch, a book that you read. It can be a lot of different events. It can also be a sequence of events that that inspires you in some way. So it's an inspiration is something that's really hard to capture. I can also share a blog with you where we investigated this topic of inspiration within our work to see how does that, how does that work, and how can you create opportunities for inspiration? Because then once you feel inspired and you feel like, oh wow, what if an alternative future is possible? And what if I can make my farming business model healthy again and actually bring back some birds and insects and healthy food for my animals or beautiful products? So it's like this. Yeah. We call it in Dutch *lukuratief perspectief* [lucrative perspective]. So it means a future that's like calling you. Um, and once you feel like there's a future that's calling you, you want to act upon it, then you feel like, Oh, what if I join this learning network, what if I start to experiment with composting? Or what if I fade out my use of pesticides and provide more natural pest management. And once you start to experiment, often in collaboration with likeminded other farmers and learning networks, and you actually get re-inspired. So it's just like you get into this positive loop like, Oh my God, I tried composting and now my soil is much healthier. This gives me so much inspiration. So I just I want to do it again. What else can I try out, you know. So once you get into this positive loop of, ok, an alternative is possible, I feel like I can get access to funding or learning or knowledge or like peers that want the same thing. Then you're in a great place because then it's such a multiply. And sometimes in very rural areas, farmers that want to do things differently they feel very alone and they feel like they're are seen as the crazy once. Like, Oh, you're such a such a loser. You're like, You become like this green farmer. And so they feel alone, so what if you connect those lonely farmers in a region and they start to feel less

alone? And then you. Yeah. You've got something going. Yeah. Yeah. I feel like I'm (incomprehensive).

I [00:35:03] That's completely fine. I just try to capture it more or less. I mean, I can listen to it again and then I try to make it a bit more clearer. But from what I understood, it's like, okay, farmers are inspired and they start changing practices, start changing values, and then they get even more inspired because they see it works and they see the positive outcomes. And so, yeah, this loop, right?

P10 [00:35:32] Um. Yeah.

I [00:35:34] Maybe I ate something like. Mm. Positive outcomes or something. I don't know how to call it.

P10 [00:35:46] Sort of feedback. Yeah, right.

I [00:35:49] And then. That kind of gets even more inspired.

P10 [00:35:58] I see if I can find that blog for you.

I [00:36:00] Yeah, that would be great. It's nice to have this information.

P10 [00:36:03] So we had a learning journey on the turn of inspiration. We call it the return of inspiration and I share it with you. I'm getting some colleagues that want to speak to me now, but let's try to see if we can still come time to finish.

I [00:36:29] Yeah, yeah, yeah. Oh, okay. Yeah, maybe. Um, so how much more time do you have?

P10 [00:36:39] Maybe 10 minutes. Is that okay?

I [00:36:41] Yeah, we can try to. I mean, you already said a lot of important things. Um, maybe we.

P10 [00:36:48] We can try again later as well if you like, but.

I [00:36:50] Yeah, I mean, I'm. That would be great, but. Yeah, let me know. Um. So is there anything among all this post-its which seems super relevant for you to speed it up a little bit?

P10 [00:37:06] And I think it's let's say let's assume that this what we said right now is like key. These are key conditions. And these key conditions could be similar for public officials, you know, people working at the municipality or. So it's about creating these spaces where people can open their mind and heart to another future and where you facilitate these multi-stakeholder processes, where they can collaborate. So it can be a farmer to farmer. But it could also be people living in an area or landscape. I mean, for us, our work is very much on bringing multiple stakeholders together in a region to see, okay, what if we reshape landscapes for biodiversity helping? But you can do the same for healthcare or education. It's about creating these co-creation spaces because these are also spaces of belonging. I will also share with you a paper that we wrote on this and and I think that's key for the farming transition and let's assume we want to create these open spaces where people can be inspired and kick into alternative action. The interventions that you need to then take on are directed towards that, so that, what you said are experimental outside-spaces, the co-creation spaces, creating a safe space where people can exchange ideas, alternatives, future perspectives. Creating these spaces of collaboration for me is a key invention and it can be between the farmers. But it could also be between farmers and their environment. People that work with they work with like the water board or, you know, their businesses or stuff like that. So it's these creating these spaces for co-creation. I think that's a key intervention. And. Yep. Yep. Because then you can start to not just discuss like project deliverables, but you can actually start to discuss like, how do we see the farm, the future of farming. (incomprehensive) Spaces for public debate and spaces for co-creation, I think is is a key intervention.

I [00:39:42] Yeah. Yeah. I kept it.

P10 [00:39:48] And let me see if I can find that paper for you.

I [00:39:51] That would be nice.

P10 [00:39:55] Yeah.

I [00:39:58] Yeah. So maybe if you. Yes. I think I would like to talk to you again, perhaps because I have a feeling we could continue a little bit.

P10 [00:40:09] Yeah. Um, so good.

I [00:40:12] I mean, I'm quite flexible. So you could propose a time when. What? That suits you? Um, I'll check my calendar.

P10 [00:40:22] Yes. How about next week, Wednesday?

I [00:40:51] Yeah. One moment. Yeah.

P10 [00:40:59] For example from three to four?

I [00:41:01] Oh, that would be perfect. Yeah.

P10 [00:41:04] Yeah.

I [00:41:04] Yeah. Sounds really good.

P10 [00:41:07] Yeah. Nice. Okay. Will you send an invite?

I [00:41:11] Yeah, I'll send an invite with a link again.

P10 [00:41:12] Perfect. Yeah. And sorry to cut you short. There was just some urgent stuff that I need to do.

I [00:41:21] No problem. I mean, I'm super glad that we can continue our talk next week, and that's perfect.

P10 [00:41:28] Okay. And I hope we can continue evolving. Yeah. Yeah.

I [00:41:32] So 3 to 4 next week. Wednesday. I send you an invite. Thank you very much.

P10 [00:41:39] Take care. Bye.

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P10 [00:19:00] Hi. I'm so sorry.

I [00:19:05] Hi.

P10 [00:19:06] I was just in a meeting and it was running late, and then I looked in the time and.

I [00:19:16] No, thank you very much for coming. I was just confused. I was scared that you're, like, in another room again. I'm like.

P10 [00:19:23] Oh, no, no, no, no, no, no.

I [00:19:26] Right. Okay. How are you?

P10 [00:19:30] Good. Yeah. And you?

I [00:19:32] Yeah, I'm a little bit tired today. So I think it's the weather. It's quite, like, humid and warm and. Yeah. Okay. I think I share my screen and we directly jump into what we did last time. Can you see it?

P10 [00:20:00] Yep, yep, Yep.

I [00:20:02] Nice. So, yeah, I think last time we started with the blue post-its, so with the conditions regarding the question, What is really necessary to transition on this one is to transition to regenerative agriculture regarding the norms and value systems. And if yeah, if I remember correctly you added or you mentioned points like the inspiration that farmers need inspiration to see regenerative agriculture and also to recognise the values of regenerative agriculture. And you also mentioned the general openness of change that is needed so that everything can happen actually, so that at the moment there is no openness of change. Um, and you also mentioned the need of an open dialogue between different stakeholders and also farmers collaboration networks and learning networks. That's what I kind of kept in mind from last time. Do you need a little bit to read yourself back into the post-its? Or how, what does it mean?

P10 [00:21:26] I remember that we talked about this. Yeah.

I [00:21:29] Yeah. And because yeah, my question would be if you want to add something. So is there anything else you think is important? Which is another condition which needs to be met for the norms and values system of agriculture to change? I think that's a question.

P10 [00:22:00] I think what we discussed last time was very much that they need to be a sense of urgency. There needs to be openness, there needs to be an open dialogue, there need to be exposing so that you get a feeling for this alternative future. Then you start to recognise that well and quite quickly connected to that is this converting into action on the ground. And then so the farmers apply regenerative practices or outcomes. That is also important. Yeah.

I [00:22:31] Okay, I will add the converting into action.

I [00:22:52] Ok, because if we, since we have this, I would like to start thinking about how could we reach these conditions. So how could an openness for change of the whole sector could be established? So what is really needed? What are interventions that are needed for this?

P10 [00:23:17] Yeah. For example, um, the German research, decade of research on biodiversity decline, especially in insect populations, you've probably read that. Right?. Are you familiar with that research?

I [00:23:38] Can you repeat the biodiversity?

P10 [00:23:42] So in in Germany, there was a decade long research on insect populations where they monitor an insect population in the rural countryside. And they published, I think three or four years ago and it sent a shock throughout the sector, realising, oh my gosh, if we lose these insects, it's almost like we've lost 70% of our insect population. And I think those kinds of reports and research findings can kind of supercharged the discussion. Mm hmm. So it's it's research, a credible research, but it can also sometimes be a movie. A book. A certain speaker on social media or so. It's like this public debate, which can either increase or decrease the openness for change.

I [00:24:43] Mm hmm. Um. Okay. I tried to add. And so wow my computer is.

P10 [00:24:53] I would say, um, public debate, informed by research, media. Yeah.

I [00:25:01] So is it related to the open dialogue between stakeholders that you already have, or is it something else?

P10 [00:25:09] So the open dialogue between stakeholders, that is really creating a space. A conscious space for people to discuss the future of agriculture. So it's very, it's a bit more directed. Whereas the public debate is almost like at a societal level.

I [00:25:25] Okay.

P10 [00:25:28] Yeah.

I [00:25:28] Okay. Okay. So informed debate perhaps. Oh, wow. And this is informed by research. I mean, now it's research under regenerative agriculture. But as you mentioned, it's also research on, for example, biodiversity, but on a related topics in the end.

P10 [00:26:15] Yes. It could be research, it could be through online and traditional media. So it could be investigative journalism, it could be TV shows, it could be a paper in the, a newspaper article. So it's like, yeah, and it's a societal, like sometimes you have, let's say, for example, in the Netherlands, we have this tradition just before Christmas where it's like, um, you know, it's like a public holiday thing where St. Nikolaus comes and the kids get presents and we have this tradition had sort of a racist element in it. And maybe ten years ago people would say, Nah, it's not racist. We can keep this element in the tradition. It's fine. But now, due to public debate and the reaction between documentary, journalists posting articles and and also in the political arena, we've had discussions about. There have been protests, people going to the streets. Um, this public debate is advancing and that's also (incomprehensive) advance. So what we thought was normal ten years ago is not normal now, what we consider to be normal agriculture and now could be different five years or ten years from now. Maybe, who knows, maybe, um, our ancestors will say, Why did you eat animals?

I [00:27:43] Yeah.

P10 [00:27:44] Or why did you kill so many animals?

I [00:27:47] Uh.

P10 [00:27:51] This is something. Yeah. And how do you shape that is a very multi vocal, uh, complex thing. And it does contribute to the openness for change.

I [00:28:03] Yeah. And what is needed to have more of these topics, for example, in the media, so in newspapers, in documentaries. So what what, what is needed for that?

P10 [00:28:22] Um, I would say free press. Um. It could be, how do you say. Um. You know what it means for that. So you need free press. You need a good. Yeah. What do you call it? Political or (incomprehensive - Dutch expression). It's like tax funded media. Oh, what is that in English? Public broadcasting. Yeah.

I [00:29:20] Mm hmm.

P10 [00:29:23] And, yeah, so free press. You need. You need civil society. So NGOs and civil society organisations that address these power imbalances and they address the problems of a certain sector.

I [00:29:51] Ok. Sorry. I think I will give up with the post-its because my laptop is so slow. So we just talk and I will try to capture it later, because otherwise I have the feeling that it's not working at the moment.

P10 [00:30:02] Okay. Okay.

I [00:30:04] And I'm more like not really focussed.

P10 [00:30:07] So I get it. Yeah.

I [00:30:10] So okay, I just leave it and we maybe we take it as inspiration. So you said civil society actors are also important to bring more of these topics into the public debate.

P10 [00:30:22] Yes, so you need a strong civil society, you need free press. You need. Um. And it connects a little bit to the open dialogue between different stakeholders. So you need to have. Apart from. Consciously organising a dialogue towards change of you. At some point in time you arrive at a point where you feel like, okay, and we recognise it's a problem and now we need to create co-creation spaces. But even before that, how do you organise public debates? Sometimes it's about organise, literally organising debate nights, and yeah, cultural events where people can discuss a certain societal topic and that needs to be an inclusive space. What you see is often that these public debates happen a lot in and around cities because that's where a lot of ideas are generated at the same time. I think a lot of change also sometimes comes from the rural side, but we don't see it as, because a lot of media. Is there (incomprehensive) [people living in rural areas/farmers?] are not as strongly heard as the voice of people living in more highly populated areas. So that's why I really like local news.

I [00:31:52] Yeah. Okay. Mm hmm. So bring local news also in the focus of debates.

P10 [00:32:08] And so that's on the public debate level. And I think interventions (incomprehensive) are really about first engaging with front runner farmers, farmers that have already or maybe even people active in the agricultural sector that are front runners. So they recognise (incomprehensive).

I [00:32:34] Sorry. But I think I have to interrupt you again. You're like, your voice is breaking again. So maybe could you call me. I have the feeling it's better.

P10 [00:32:50] You have my number or you give me yours.

I [00:32:54] Um I can also call your I think with the number from last time. Okay. I think I call you now.

P10 [00:33:18] Hi.

I [00:33:19] Hi. Okay.

P10 [00:33:25] This is good, yeah?

I [00:33:26] Yeah, it's much better. I can listen to it much better than. Sorry.

P10 [00:33:33] Yeah. So we had (incomprehensible), and then I think another layer of interventions is directed towards the people active in the agricultural sector.

I [00:33:42] Mm hmm.

P10 [00:33:43] Farmers. Suppliers of inputs. Maybe the Ministry of Agriculture. So how do you then connect, like innovation networks of people that (incomprehensible) need [?] to change, that already started to kick into action both in terms of bottom-up change, but also in terms of regime level change so that the minister, Ministry of Agriculture, municipalities, in the Netherlands we have water boards, those are governmental entities focussed on water management. And with farmers that really bringing those front runner farmers together in strong networks, so learn from each other, to exchange experiences, to scale up their innovations and then become this strong bottom up wave of change that will inevitably meet some barriers.

I [00:34:38] Okay. Nice. I was wondering, because here are some post-its, I'm not sure if you can read them, regarding education of regenerative agriculture is super broad, but these were post-its that were mentioned in the workshops last year regarding norms and values system, and I think some of them fit to what you're already said. So for example, influencers I think is kind of this media use approach, but would you think that for example, like these two post-its are more on the on the law and policy level are also important. So really have like bans or have like use a taxation subsidy system. Is that relevant for the norms and value system to change or do you think, Not at all.

P10 [00:35:47] Um yeah, I think so. I mean, policies are informed by norms and values that are shifting. But if you set new policies, it can also influence norms of values. So I think it's a bit of it's a bit (incomprehensible), but it can really normalise these things. Yeah. Yeah, that's so, um, it's a, it's in a, in a way a response to a public debate shifting, but it can also normalise standards. Um, so yeah. Yeah.

I [00:36:29] So if there is like a movement going on, law and policy could bring this movement like into a law into like a formalised written thing so that other people can orient again. So this is a kind of feedback loop.

P10 [00:36:46] Okay. So for example, um, around for example, I do call that static help. So when I buy a bottle of plastic and I deliver it, I get €0.10 back.

I [00:36:59] Yeah. Mm hmm.

P10 [00:37:01] And there's a word for that. It's probably taxation, it has to do with taxation. So if there's a new law that says you need to pay for a bottle of plastic water, then once that's introduced, it starts to become a norm, because then it's normal to bring back the plastic bottle of water instead of throwing it in nature.

I [00:37:25] Mm hmm.

P10 [00:37:27] So there's this kind of this (incomprehensive)

I [00:37:31] Yeah. I see.

P10 [00:37:32] And that law came into force because there was a lot of plastic waste.

I [00:37:37] Mm hmm.

P10 [00:37:38] Which was, which was normal because people found it normal to throw our plastic waste, but then there was a lot of debating around, Is this normal day, Do we agree that this is normal or do we want to minimise the plastic soup and thus want laws and force and I mean paper, they often say paper is patient. So what you often see is that laws and standards and rules often follow societal change, but. So that I think it's like, how it normally goes. As laws always coming to, in fact, sometimes a little bit too late. We first need to realise things are going wrong and we need more rules and then it takes ten years to develop a law for this or, you know, and it needs to be voted upon. And the European Union is taking longer. But it can also, once the law is in effect, it can reshape the way we organise ourselves within society and thereby normalise certain norms and values.

I [00:38:45] Mm hmm.

P10 [00:38:47] Okay. Because then it's written in law and then we agree upon, okay, this is our law system and we follow the law. And so it normalises norms and values.

I [00:38:58] Okay. Nice. And if you read through this post-its that are here, is there anything which kind of like attracts you or where you think, okay, that's also maybe relevant or not relevant, or do you have any comments to the existing intervention?

P10 [00:39:33] Makes a lot of sense. That makes a lot of sense. There's nothing in there that doesn't make sense.

I [00:39:46] And how would you connect these elements to what you said before? Is it possible to connect them?

P10 [00:40:07] Yeah. What reconfirms for me is that the way in which norms and values are shaped in society is a very messy and (incomprehensive) process. That democracy is very messy. Mm hmm. So we never gonna reach a state in society where everybody agrees on everything.

I [00:40:26] Mm hmm.

P10 [00:40:27] We need to have this debate, this public arena, where we can debate things and we can say, is this still true for us. Or do we realise something needs to change? Do we believe that the market will solve everything, or do we believe that the government does play a role? Mm hmm. Do we believe in animal [?] change or do we believe in? Yeah, so it's like this this. It's a very messy process, but there are re-occurring. And it has to do with the role of, um, the market, the role of the government and the role of society. Those three, the Golden Triangle, the golden, the Golden Triangle or something. So it has to do with those three actors, so the markets, the government and society and those three actors interact with each other. And they need to keep each other in balance. So the government is made up of a judicial system and different ministries and the Parliament. And they they are the caretakers of society. They need to create rules for engagement and provide support to the weak in a democratic society. And they have the market, which has been for the last few decades, we have had this longstanding belief that the market would solve everything which is privatised the trade system, if just privatised the health care system, the market rules everything else. And what we're seeing now is that it creates a lot of inequality. There's some people that win and there's a large group that loses. So we put a lot of emphasis on the market solving our problems, and I think we're now trying to rebalance that. So we're trying to give back that power to society. We're trying to put that power into the face [?] Of government. So it requires a shift in what we prioritise, and how we organise our society. And as it is agriculture, we've got a lot of schooling and highly industrial agriculture to feed the world and then we realise we don't have to feed the world first

of all. And this model is just unsustainable. It's not going to last forever. So what do we do now? And what is the role of commercial actors benefiting from this, from farmers with their input? Models selling fertilisers and seed and the whole industry around the farmer is making so much money off of the farmer. Is that what we want? And you have these you have grassroots organisations all over Europe that want to give more power to small scale farming and food sovereignty and large agri firms making a lot of money off of the farmer. Mm hmm. Uh. And I don't know if I'm in a little bubble, but I feel like there's a there's a shift in the public opinion about farming. And even the ministers are realising under pressure by the European Union and the Netherlands that the current global culture is not gonna last. We need less emissions, maybe, maybe less animals. We need to rebalance, export and consumption. Causing loops of nutrients. So it's not just one or two people that are really just like green left shouting. We need to do something that's actually becoming more mainstream realisation that this is not going to last, that we will need to change something. But then the question is what is this a government defined as strong after decades of rolling back responsibility for putting it in the hands of the market? And you see this, that they're really trying to find their feet as a as a government to to create these safe spaces of a dialogue. And actually, we've been advised by the Ministry of Agriculture to also talk to them about how can you create these open spaces for dialogue instead of polarisation?

I [00:45:03] Mm hmm.

P10 [00:45:07] And I think the government's trying to say find its role again, like, how can we fulfil that role? How can we organise that at a national level or a regional level, at a village level even? And how do we create that space again? Instead (incomprehensive). So. Yeah.

I [00:45:24] Yeah, yeah. Oh, very nice. Makes a lot of sense to me.

P10 [00:45:30] I have the feeling I'm talking so much.

P10 [00:45:30] No, it's completely fine. I'm. I'm just making editing notes notes because I don't take notes on the board, But, you know, that's a very, very good. And so do you have any more, interventions? Otherwise I would continue. So on measures how we could change the value system.

P10 [00:46:01] No, I think this is good.

I [00:46:03] Nice. So then my next question would be, um, it's a little bit I'm not quite super clear, but the question is, so what can result from if we imagine, okay, we have like a changed norms and value system, what are the consequences? So what happens concretely? So what do we want to achieve? Maybe also and also considering maybe other topics or other areas? I put them up here

again. So education, law and policy, we already talked about, um, finance, information feedbacks, localisation and decentralisation. And so can you think of anything?

P10 [00:46:54] What happens if the conditions are fulfilled, how would this influence the transition? I think the consequences if the conditions are met, I would say, there is a stronger social fabric within the farming community.

I [00:47:12] Can you repeat that social fabric? I want to do.

P10 [00:47:15] So there is a stronger and stronger social fabric in the farming communities. As more and more people, more and more farmers are connected around these alternative models and not organised around this intensive aspect of agriculture, but around this alternative model of agriculture. So there are strong networks. There is a growing knowledge base of farmers experimenting with alternative agriculture. So there are more and more examples of how you can do it differently. And those examples are starting to become bigger as well, not just pilots. And I think what we also could see happening is that large agricultural actors and commercial actors are starting to also transition. So they're starting to also realise our model of making money is not going to last. So they need to also join the transition like the banks or input companies are already seeing that.

I [00:48:29] Mm hmm.

P10 [00:48:31] So it's both, the bottom up change becomes more bigger, it becomes a bigger wave and the regime player players are starting to also take along. Yeah.

I [00:48:43] Nice.

P10 [00:48:49] And I think that from the European level and from a national level, there's more and more guidance in terms of rules and regulations on how you can transition towards this alternative future as a farmer. There's more clarity, more consistency, maybe on what are the next steps.

I [00:49:11] Mm hmm.

P10 [00:49:13] So you can also be rewarded for taking sustainable steps in terms of subsidies. Um. I wouldn't be surprised if we are. I think we're seeing that in the Netherlands especially. Well, that we have a period of a bit of backlash where than the mainstream actively benefited from that old model of farming certainly protest. Which we're seeing in the Netherlands, we had this big political winns of a more conservative party. So you always have this like to seps forward one step back.

I [00:50:01] Mm. And so, yeah, that would actually relate to the next question, because the next question is, um, so we talked a lot about how could the transition be happening. But I was also wondering what our current, uh, I think we were like cut off. And I can't call you again, I think my phone didn't allow it. I think it. Did you try to call?

P10 [00:51:16] Are you calling me?

I [00:51:17] No, I think I can't, actually.

P10 [00:51:22] Okay. Can you give me your number?

I [00:51:24] Ah sure. Sorry for this mess. Hello?

P10 [00:52:09] Yeah.

I [00:52:10] Oh, perfect. Okay. Thank you. Sorry. I kind of, um. Yeah. So, yeah, the question was. Yeah, we talked a lot about how it could I enhance the transition, but I was also wondering about what our current barriers. Why, why does the transition process is so slow? What is kind of holding it back? And so one thing you just said is like, okay, there are always opposite, political, yeah, wins or conservative thinking, which oppose this progressive, um, idea of regenerative agriculture. Is there anything else?

P10 [00:52:58] I think indeed, I said, the opposing forces, that's something you need to be aware of. So there's going to be vested interests that will protest. So that's one thing. Another thing I think is, um, when when we're in a transition, like we are in now, in society, not just on agriculture, but on our whole economic system, price fluctuations and high levels of inequality will make it difficult for a lot of people to also pay a higher price for food, for example. Our food is way too cheap. So one of the hindering factors could be that not everybody can afford higher prices. Or is not willing to pay a higher price to spend. I see a lot of policy barrier right now. Our whole regulatory system, especially about agriculture, is based on a certain mode of agriculture. Just to give you an example, in the Netherlands, land is either nature or high value agricultural land, but there's nothing in between. But if you look at the challenge of agricultural, agroforestry, agro ecology, it's a mix of nature and farming, but it doesn't fit into the regulatory function of that government. So it's very hard for farmers to step into that middle space where there's no rules yet. They need to obey by the rules for conventional agriculture. So it's hard for them to move out of those little boxes and get access to public services that only fit that in box. So, so regulatory, old regulatory systems are holding us back a little bit and takes time to change those. Access to land, access to finance, definitely. So we see a lot of, um. regenerative businesses that want to scale up, but they're either too small for big investments or

they're too big for small grants. This missing middle is a thing. And for farmers specifically, it's access to transition finance. Because if you want to transition to a regenerative system, it takes a couple of years for your soil to be restored and to actually create a similar level of yield. And that's a valley of death, that's how they call it, need a lot of transition finance, and that's flexible and long term and accessible. Oh, yeah. Okay. These are complex questions.

I [00:56:10] But it's good. I mean, you already said a lot.

P10 [00:56:16] Yeah. Barriers. I think short termism is a barrier, so short term thinking. So investors want short term return on investment. We're very we're living in a short term society where we want short term results. But if you look at regenerative agriculture and ecosystem restoration, it takes time. And maybe we're not going to make as much money in a short amount of time as we used to in the old system. And maybe we need to start to except this.

I [00:56:54] And change a little bit this thinking of, okay, we have to accept the long term in a way. Okay. Yes.

P10 [00:57:03] Another barrier is market access. So that our whole market is also organised around bulk production. So tons of made tons of soy. And if we want to diversify our farming systems to kinds of crops from one farm, how do we organise that supply chain effectively? Because then a farmer might have ten or 15 different crops that he or she wants to sell. And how do you do that with monoculture markets and processing and processing infrastructure?

I [00:57:53] Okay. Yeah. Very good. So I think that's my last question. I will quickly check. Um, yeah. maybe one, one little last question. So, what do you think for the norms and values system from all what you said last time and this time, what is, uh, what are the most important processes or what is really the most important aspect in this whole norms and value change aspect or thinking?

P10 [00:58:25] If I would, if I need to pick one thing, I would say creating a space for dialogue and listening to each other.

I [00:58:36] Yeah. Okay. I expect that

P10 [00:58:39] That could be at community level but also at the national level. So creating these safe spaces of dialogue to decrease polarisation and to create who we think we are as human beings and what we want our society to look. Creating a lot of those spaces would be my number one.

I [00:59:01] Yeah. Mm hmm. Okay. Then I think I, I don't have any more questions regarding this like or regarding the content of this map. Do you have anything else you want to share?

P10 [00:59:27] No, I think it's super valuable research. I'm looking forward to see the results.

I [00:59:32] Yeah. Nice. Yeah, I. I'm actually. So I will revise this and clear this up and try to create a map out of it. And if that would be okay for you, I would send it to you again just to have, like, a quick feedback. And of course, in the end, if I finished with everything, I would also share the my thesis and the results. Yeah.

P10 [00:59:55] Perfect.

I [00:59:56] Yeah. Okay. Nice. Thank you very much for your time. Thank you for doing this.

P10 [01:00:01] Sorry for being late.

I [01:00:03] No worries. I mean, we managed perfectly in time, so it's fine.

P10 [01:00:07] Okay. Okay.

I [01:00:08] All right. Okay. Have a good afternoon. Bye.

P10 [01:00:23] Yes. Bye. Bye.